

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Exploring quantum paths on rhythmspaces

María Aguado Yáñez

Supervisors: Daniel Gómez-Marín & Sergi Jordà

Co-Supervisor: Karl Jansen

August 2024

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Motivation	1
1.2	Objectives	4
1.3	Structure of the Report	5
2	State of the Art	6
2.1	Rhythmspaces	6
2.1.1	What is a Rhythmspace?	6
2.1.2	Rhythmspace generation	6
2.1.3	Rhythmspaces' State of the Art	8
2.2	Quantum Paths	8
2.2.1	Introduction to Quantum Mechanics	8
2.2.2	Introduction to Quantum Computing	16
2.2.3	Quantum Random Walks	22
2.2.4	1D Discrete Quantum Random Walks	22
2.2.5	2D Discrete Quantum Random Walks	25
2.2.6	QRWs in Music: State of the Art	27
3	Methodology & Results	29
3.1	Stage 1: From Hilbert spaces to Rhythmspaces	29
3.1.1	Encoding positions in the rhythmspace as qubits	30
3.1.2	Handling the pixel resolution	31
3.1.3	Implementing the circuits	34

3.2	Stage 2: Biasing with potentials	36
3.2.1	Quantum feedback based on potential gradients	37
3.2.2	Purely Random Paths	38
3.2.3	Linear Potential	39
3.2.4	Gaussian Potential	40
3.2.5	Gaussian Potential: Inertial Dynamics	41
3.3	Stage 3: Sonification	42
3.3.1	Resampling the paths for sonification	43
3.3.2	Sending the paths as MIDI messages	44
4	Discussion & Conclusion	46
	Bibliography	50

Acknowledgement

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the Music Technology Group at Universitat Pompeu Fabra and to my supervisors, Daniel and Sergi, for allowing me to merge my ideas with their research. This gratitude also extends to DESY and the Center for Quantum Technology and Applications team in Zeuthen for providing resources and knowledge, with special thanks to my co-supervisor there, Karl, for his solid feedback and help.

I would also like to thank my Sound and Music Computing Master's friends for enriching my learning process and keeping me motivated. Lastly, to my family, I extend my deepest thanks for their never-ending and unconditional support.

Abstract

Continuing the pioneering work in the novel field of Quantum Computer Music, this thesis aims to sonify quantum random walks as rhythmic sequences using the Rhythmspaces software, a 2D visual interactive tool for rhythm generation and exploration.

The methodology includes three stages: The first stage involves designing quantum computing algorithms and mapping the qubit space to the rhythm space. The second stage focuses on generating and visualizing quantum walks on a pixel interface, adding potentials to bias the walks, and introducing more complex shapes and trajectories. The third stage addresses the sonification of these generated paths by generating MIDI drum pattern messages and sending them to a DAW.

This tool serves as a proof of concept for scalable quantum computing algorithm design in audio processing and music applications, illustrating the mutual benefits of interdisciplinary approaches in art and science.

Keywords: Quantum Computer Music; Quantum Computing; Rhythmspaces

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

As Quantum Computers continue to gain importance across different disciplines, such as in material science and machine learning [1], a new field known as Quantum Computer Music has emerged, establishing a research community over the past five years. The book "Quantum Computer Music: Foundations and Initial Experiments" [2], published in 2022, and the two International Symposiums on Quantum Computing and Musical Creativity (ISQCMC) held in 2021 [3] and 2023 [4], have gathered scientists and ideas from around the world to create a consensus and establish a domain where quantum computers can be used as unique tools for generating and interpreting music. Interdisciplinary approaches significantly benefit research, and music technology can be explored from a new perspective through the formalism of Quantum Computing.

Music has consistently evolved alongside technology. The moment a new technology is created, people around the world explore its properties for a wide variety of purposes, including artistic and creative ones. The impact of computers and modern electronics on the creation of music has been very significant over the past century. In the realm of music technology, Max Mathews (1926-2011)[7] developed the first computer program for generating digital audio waveforms in 1957 [8], only twenty

Figure 1: *Where quantum physics meets music* [5], a Quantum Computer Music concert example given in December 2022 at the Goethe-Institut in London. The Q1Synth [6], a synthesizer based on quantum computing principles, is shown in the background and was played in real time.

years after Alan Turing introduced the modern computer concept. Mathews inspired musicians globally to create music using computational algorithms, setting an inspiration for well-known computer scientists such as Miller Puckette (1959-today), the developer of Pure Data and Max MSP ¹[9]. Within the compositional realm, remarkable composers such as Pierre Schaeffer (1910-1955) and his *musique concrète* [10], Iannis Xenakis (1922-2001) and his stochastic music [11], or Karlheinz Stockhausen (1928-2007) with his innovative electroacoustic techniques [12], explored intricate relations that can be found between modern technological approaches and music. The rapid integration of AI into the music creation process is also evident. Just as these examples of revolutionary applications of technologies in music occurred, the Quantum Computer Music community is focused on developing all the necessary foundations to enable the running of quantum algorithms for music applications when more powerful quantum computers become available in the coming years.

There are three fundamental reasons to exploit Quantum Computing for music applications. Firstly, art can be expanded when new technologies and scientific concepts are used creatively. Moreover, phenomena within quantum mechanics yield math-

¹Max MSP and Pure Data are the most popular visual programming languages for the creation of computer music.

Figure 2: Drawing from *Pithoprakta*, a piece by Iannis Xenakis for string orchestra. ‘Pithoprakta’ means ‘actions through probability’ and is based on stochastic processes [13].

emational results, such as certain probability distributions or stochastic processes involving random numbers, which cannot be reproduced by a classical computer². This allows musicians to explore new ways of composing music and crafting sound through a different formalism with special properties. Secondly, sonifying abstract mathematical spaces and physical systems can help the research community understand them better and gain more insight. Music, being highly intuitive for many people, can aid in this understanding. For example, it is common to find an audience that, despite not necessarily having knowledge in music theory, can harmonize melodies at a concert. Exploring physics through intuitive perceptual approaches, similar to creating visual diagrams or graphs, is a powerful tool for scientists³. Lastly, making quantum formalism more accessible to the general public through music can lead to innovative teaching methods, transforming dense lectures on quantum mechanics into interactive auditory sessions.

For all these reasons, this thesis aims to implement quantum algorithms within a rhythm-generative tool currently under development by the Music Technology Group at Universitat Pompeu Fabra. The intention of this project is to serve as a

²See [14], [15] as examples of detailed explanations on the mathematical differences between quantum and classical probability distributions.

³See example in [16] of the sonification of Rabi oscillations, which are a type of probability amplitude oscillation in quantum mechanics.

proof-of-concept for algorithms designed to explore multidimensional music spaces that can be easily scaled up to larger quantum computing systems.

1.2 Objectives

Following to the previous motivations, the main objective of this master thesis is to create a proof-of-concept tool that helps people understand quantum trajectories by listening to music. To achieve this, several specific objectives have been set:

1. **Quantum Random Walk Algorithms for Music Generation:** This objective involves developing reliable and scalable quantum random walk algorithms for music applications. The procedures described in this document show how quantum computing concepts, especially quantum random walks, can be used to create music. These algorithms are designed to handle large and complex musical spaces by utilizing qubits instead of classical computing bits.
2. **Sonification for Physics Research:** This objective aims to assist the physics research community by turning physical systems into sound, helping researchers understand abstract concepts through listening.
3. **Sonification for Public Understanding of Physics:** This objective focuses on using sound to help the general public understand difficult mathematical and physics ideas, making complex concepts easier to grasp.
4. **New Methods for Creating Sounds and Composing Music:** The unique feature of these methods is that they are based on quantum random walks. Quantum random walks take advantage of basic properties of quantum mechanics that can't be replicated on classical computers. Therefore, the sound algorithms developed for quantum computers offer new perspectives, new ways of composing music, and the creation of unique sounds.
5. **Audiovisual Interactive Interfaces for Exploring Physics Concepts:** This objective aims to build interactive tools that allow users to explore and

understand physics concepts through images and sound, enhancing their appreciation of the relationship between quantum mechanics and music.

Through these objectives, the thesis aims to connect complex quantum mechanical concepts with intuitive musical experiences, helping both the scientific community and the general public better understand quantum trajectories.

1.3 Structure of the Report

Chapter 1 introduces the field of Quantum Computer Music and presents the intention and objectives of this project.

Chapter 2 explains the state of the art of rhythmspaces and quantum random walks in music. Before delving into the current state of these topics, the chapter provides detailed explanations of the main ideas and concepts needed to understand the state of the art. Regarding rhythmspaces, an explanation of the tool and how it generates rhythms is introduced. Regarding quantum random walks, a detailed introductory explanation of the principles and core concepts in quantum mechanics and quantum computing is also presented.

Chapter 3 delves into the methodologies followed for this project. It is divided into three stages. Stage 1 explains how the quantum random walk algorithms are designed and how they are mapped to the rhythmpace. Stage 2 explains how potential fields are introduced into the rhythmpace to bias the quantum random walk paths and draw shapes and trajectories. Stage 3 explains the sonification mappings and how the paths are transformed into MIDI messages to be sent to a DAW.

Chapter 4 gathers the conclusions and final discussions on this project.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

2.1 Rhythmspaces

2.1.1 What is a Rhythmspace?

In the realm of music production, DJs, producers, and musicians often struggle to find and select suitable rhythms from vast lists and sound archives. A *rhythmspace* [17] is a tool that offers an intuitive, visual, and organized approach to generate and choose rhythms efficiently. Users can access this space of rhythms and navigate it interactively through a user-friendly interface, clicking with the mouse on a point in the space to generate a rhythm. The video in [18] illustrates how this tool is used.

2.1.2 Rhythmspace generation

In references [17], [19], and [20], the concept and generation of rhythmspaces are explained in detail. [19] delves into the generation of these spaces, while [20] focuses more on the 2D visualization. [17] is a more extensive and detailed work on rhythmspaces that gathers information from the two aforementioned papers. A brief summary of the key ideas in these references is presented in the following paragraphs.

The initial space is constructed with a set of predefined points or rhythmic patterns. *Descriptors* are then extracted from these patterns to represent their characteris-

Figure 3: Rhythmspace interface. The triangles represent the Delaunay Triangulation through which the interpolation of rhythms is made. The user clicks on an arbitrary position, and the interpolation is done according to the triangle where the point falls.

tics. One example of a descriptor is *StepD*, which measures the sum of steps in a pattern containing at least one onset, divided by the total number of steps.

A *Multitask Lasso Regression* is performed to decide which descriptors best describe this 2D space. This regression sets the coordinates of the patterns in each space as a target (X) and the matrix of descriptors as variables ($Y_1, Y_2, Y_3\dots$), and returns a subset of variables and weights that maximise correlation of a subset of descriptors with the positions of the patterns. Thus, we can associate a vector of descriptor values with each point on our space.

To organize the space effectively, *similarity tests* are conducted on a sample of individuals, who rate the similarity between various rhythm patterns on a scale of 1 to 10. The similarity values are then transformed into distances. These similarity matrices serve as the basis for constructing a 2D space using *Multidimensional Scaling*, reducing the dimensionality while preserving the distances obtained from the similarity tests.

What is left is filling up this space by interpolating, since we only have a few points. This interpolation is done by using *Delaunay Triangulation*. This method builds triangles from the initial rhythms and computes weighted interpolated values for a given point that falls within one of this triangles (see 3). Different algorithms can be used to perform the interpolation and generate the new rhythm.

It is important to note that the rhythms used to develop this tool follow to a 4:4 meter. Consequently, it does not account for a full spectrum of rhythmic types and patterns. While Western music predominantly employs 4:4 meters, other global regions rely on more varied, often irregular or complex, rhythmic structures. It is also worth mentioning that the similarity tests used to construct the rhythm space are based on the perceptual aspects of these patterns. However, such perceptions may be influenced or biased by one's cultural background as well (chapter 10 in [21] explores how the context and the environment influence meter perception).

2.1.3 Rhythmspaces' State of the Art

The latest developments to the rhythmspaces tool include its integration as a Virtual Studio Technology (VST) plugin within a Digital Audio Workstation (DAW) [22] and the incorporation of user-generated monophonic rhythm contours that translate into polyphonic drum patterns, in order to link the tapped contours to positions within the space [23].

The rhythm space used in this thesis includes the contours in [23], and the VST adaptation in [22] serves as an example of how the introduction of quantum paths within a rhythm generative tool could be shaped into a DAW-compatible tool.

2.2 Quantum Paths

2.2.1 Introduction to Quantum Mechanics

Wave Functions, Superposition & Measurements

Since the beginning of the XXth century, a revolutionary field has been developed in physics: the field of *Quantum Mechanics* [24]. Quantum Mechanics is a theory in physics that provides a description of nature at the scale of atoms and subatomic particles. This theory presents some fundamental features that distinguish it from Classical Mechanics, and its logic and interpretability are completely different.

Among other properties, such as quantization or uncertainty, one of the most re-

markable phenomena in Quantum Mechanics is the *superposition*. This is going to be one of the most relevant concepts used in the logic of this thesis. Particles in Quantum Mechanics are described through their *wave functions*, which are a mathematical description of a quantum state in an isolated quantum system. The wave function is a complex-valued probability amplitude, and the *probabilities* for the possible results of measurements made on the system can be derived from it. In the following example

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle, \quad |\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = 1, \quad (2.1)$$

ψ is the wave function, and $|0\rangle, |1\rangle$ are the possible states in which the particle may be after measuring. *Measuring* in Quantum Mechanics consists of testing or manipulating a physical system to yield a numerical result. In other words, to make its wave function collapse into a result to get rid of the superposition. Thus, before measuring the state is in a superposition of states, each of them having a certain probability to be the actual result after measuring. Each state's probability corresponds to its squared coefficient in the wave function, and all the squared coefficients summed up must return a total probability of 1.

In more general terms, a wave function¹ is described as

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_i \alpha_i |i\rangle, \quad \sum_i |\alpha_i|^2 = 1. \quad (2.2)$$

Example 1

Let's consider a simple example of a wave function formed by a superposition of two states

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} |0\rangle + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{3}} |1\rangle, \quad \left| \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \right|^2 + \left| \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{3}} \right|^2 = 1.$$

¹This is a discrete wave function. In more general terms, wave functions can be continuous and thus described through integrals and smooth functions.

If this wave function was measured, it would collapse with the following probabilities to each of the two states

$$p(|0\rangle) = \frac{1}{3}, \quad p(|1\rangle) = \frac{2}{3}.$$

It is important to note that repeated measurements on identically prepared systems are required to statistically estimate the probability of each possible outcome. The relative frequency of each outcome across many measurements converges to the true probability.

Hilbert spaces & Bracket Notation

A wave function ψ associated with a particle lives on a complex space known as **Hilbert Space**², \mathcal{H} . The different forms that a wave function can take are defined and contained in its given Hilbert space. Thus, the states are the basis state vectors that conform the space where the wave function lies.

The type of notation used in Quantum Mechanics to label vectors is called the **Bracket Notation**. In 2.1, the wave function is a **ket vector** formed by a linear combination of two other ket vectors, where each of them corresponds to

$$|0\rangle \equiv \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad |1\rangle \equiv \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.3)$$

which are the basis vectors $\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2\}$ of the 2-dimensional Hilbert space. The corresponding **bra vector** $\langle\psi|$ is the Hermitian conjugate (complex conjugate transpose) of the ket vector

$$\langle\psi| = \alpha^* \langle 0| + \beta^* \langle 1| \quad (2.4)$$

where α^* and β^* are the complex conjugates of α and β , respectively. Thus, the

²Not every Hilbert space is complex. A Hilbert space is a complete vector space with an inner product that allows for the generalization of Euclidean geometry to infinite dimensions. While Hilbert spaces can be either real or complex, those used in quantum mechanics are specifically complex.

basis vectors written as bras are

$$\langle 0| \equiv \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}^T = (1 \ 0), \quad \langle 1| \equiv \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}^T = (0 \ 1), \quad (2.5)$$

and a set of basis vectors in a Hilbert space has to be **orthonormal**, such that

$$\langle i|j \rangle = \delta_{ij}. \quad (2.6)$$

Within a Hilbert space, the **inner product**, also known as the scalar product, is a measure of the "overlap" between two quantum states. For two states $|\psi\rangle$ and $|\phi\rangle$, the inner product is denoted as $\langle\psi|\phi\rangle$ and is a complex number. It is defined as

$$\langle\psi|\phi\rangle = \sum_i \alpha_i^* \beta_i, \quad (2.7)$$

where α_i^* is the complex conjugate of the coefficient of $|i\rangle$ in $|\psi\rangle$, and β_i is the coefficient of $|i\rangle$ in $|\phi\rangle$.

The **outer product**, also known as the dyadic product, produces an operator from two states. For states $|\psi\rangle$ and $|\phi\rangle$, the outer product is denoted as $|\psi\rangle\langle\phi|$ and is defined as:

$$|\psi\rangle\langle\phi| = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \\ \vdots \end{pmatrix} (\beta_1^*, \beta_2^*, \dots) \quad (2.8)$$

This results in a matrix whose elements are given by $\alpha_i \beta_j^*$.

Example 2

Let $|\psi\rangle$ and $|\phi\rangle$ be two quantum states

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle, \quad |\phi\rangle = \gamma|0\rangle + \delta|1\rangle.$$

Then the scalar product $\langle\psi|\phi\rangle$ is

$$\langle\psi|\phi\rangle = (\alpha^*\langle 0| + \beta^*\langle 1|)(\gamma|0\rangle + \delta|1\rangle).$$

Expanding this, we get

$$\langle \psi | \phi \rangle = \alpha^* \gamma \langle 0|0 \rangle + \alpha^* \delta \langle 0|1 \rangle + \beta^* \gamma \langle 1|0 \rangle + \beta^* \delta \langle 1|1 \rangle.$$

Using the orthonormality of the basis vectors ($\langle 0|0 \rangle = 1$, $\langle 1|1 \rangle = 1$, $\langle 0|1 \rangle = 0$, and $\langle 1|0 \rangle = 0$), this simplifies to

$$\langle \psi | \phi \rangle = \alpha^* \gamma + \beta^* \delta.$$

Using the same states $|\psi\rangle$ and $|\phi\rangle$, the outer product $|\psi\rangle \langle \phi|$ is

$$|\psi\rangle \langle \phi| = (\alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle)(\gamma^* \langle 0| + \delta^* \langle 1|) = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \gamma^* & \delta^* \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha\gamma^* & \alpha\delta^* \\ \beta\gamma^* & \beta\delta^* \end{pmatrix}.$$

Operations on states within a Hilbert space in Quantum Mechanics are performed through matrices called **Operators**. In bracket notation, an operator \hat{A} acting on a state $|\psi\rangle$ is written as $\hat{A}|\psi\rangle$. Operators can be represented in matrix form, and their action on states can be described using inner and outer products.

For a given operator \hat{A} , its matrix elements in a basis $\{|i\rangle\}$ are given by

$$A_{ij} = \langle i | \hat{A} | j \rangle = \sum_{i,j} A_{ij} |i\rangle \langle j|. \quad (2.9)$$

When an operator \hat{A} acts on a state $|\psi\rangle$, the resulting state $|\phi\rangle$ is

$$|\phi\rangle = \hat{A}|\psi\rangle = \sum_{i,j} A_{ij} \alpha_j |i\rangle. \quad (2.10)$$

Example 3

Consider the Pauli-X operator \hat{X} , which acts on a wave function such as the

one in 2.1. Its matrix representation is

$$\hat{X} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Let's see first how the Pauli-X operator acts on the computational basis vectors $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$

$$\hat{X}|0\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = |1\rangle,$$

$$\hat{X}|1\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = |0\rangle.$$

Then, the action of the Pauli-X operator on $|\psi\rangle$ is

$$\hat{X}|\psi\rangle = \hat{X}(\alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle) = \alpha\hat{X}|0\rangle + \beta\hat{X}|1\rangle = \beta|0\rangle + \alpha|1\rangle.$$

In matrix form, this can be written as

$$\hat{X}|\psi\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha \\ \beta \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \beta \\ \alpha \end{pmatrix}.$$

Tensor Product & Entanglement

Hilbert spaces can be composed through tensor products to yield higher-dimensional spaces as follows

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_1 \otimes \mathcal{H}_2. \quad (2.11)$$

When composing Hilbert spaces, the basis vectors of the new space are generated by applying tensor products between the basis vectors of the lower-dimensional spaces. In the following example, a 4-dimensional Hilbert space is built by doing the tensor product of a 2-dimensional with itself.

Example 4

Let $\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2\}$ be the basis vectors of a 2-dimensional space, where

$$\mathbf{e}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{e}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The tensor product of these basis vectors results in a 4-dimensional space with the following basis vectors

$$\mathbf{e}_1 \otimes \mathbf{e}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{e}_1 \otimes \mathbf{e}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{e}_2 \otimes \mathbf{e}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{e}_2 \otimes \mathbf{e}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

In bracket notation, these basis vectors can be written as

$$|00\rangle = |0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle,$$

$$|01\rangle = |0\rangle \otimes |1\rangle,$$

$$|10\rangle = |1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle,$$

$$|11\rangle = |1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle.$$

Thus, the 4-dimensional space spanned by the tensor product of the basis vectors \mathbf{e}_1 and \mathbf{e}_2 of the original 2-dimensional space has the basis vectors $\{|00\rangle, |01\rangle, |10\rangle, |11\rangle\}$.

Another crucial concept in Quantum Mechanics is the *entanglement*. This is a phenomenon where two or more particles are linked in a way that their properties become correlated, such that the quantum state of each particle cannot be described

independently of the state of the others. Instead, a combined quantum state must be used for the entire system. In other words, the particles become "entangled". This concept is central to the understanding of quantum mechanics and has been demonstrated in experimental settings [25].

States that are not entangled are called *separable*. A quantum state of two particles is called separable (or product state) if it can be written as the tensor product of the states of each individual particle. On the other hand, a quantum state is called **entangled** if it cannot be written as a simple product of the states of individual particles.

Example 5

Consider two wave functions in the states $|\psi\rangle$ and $|\phi\rangle$

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle, \quad |\phi\rangle = \gamma|0\rangle + \delta|1\rangle$$

The combined state $|\psi\rangle \otimes |\phi\rangle$ of these two wave functions is

$$|\Psi_{\text{sep}}\rangle = (\alpha|0\rangle + \beta|1\rangle) \otimes (\gamma|0\rangle + \delta|1\rangle) = \alpha\gamma|00\rangle + \alpha\delta|01\rangle + \beta\gamma|10\rangle + \beta\delta|11\rangle.$$

In this separable case, if the wave function ψ is measured, both its states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ are entangled with a certain probability to the two possible states of the second wave function ϕ .

As opposed to this separable state, one of the most famous examples of an entangled state is the Bell state

$$|\Psi_{\text{ent}}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|00\rangle + |11\rangle)$$

In this state, the measurement outcomes of the two wave functions are perfectly correlated. If ψ is measured to be in the state $|0\rangle$, ϕ will also be found in the

state $|0\rangle$. Similarly, if ϕ is measured to be in the state $|1\rangle$, ψ will also be found in the state $|1\rangle$.

Entanglement is mathematically interesting and a fundamental aspect of what makes quantum mechanics special because it exhibits non-classical correlations that are stronger than any correlations possible in classical physics, making it a key feature in distinguishing quantum systems from classical ones.

2.2.2 Introduction to Quantum Computing

Qubits

Later on, towards the end of the XXth century, Quantum Mechanics started to merge with Computer Science. Physicists searched for computer techniques and models that could exploit quantum properties to become more efficient or to solve problems that could not be solved through classical computers. Thus, the *Quantum Computing* field was born. This field revolves around the concept of superposition to create algorithms. Classical computers use bits as fundamental units of binary information, whereas in quantum computers unit is what is known as *qubit*. A qubit is a quantum state whose wave function is in a superposition of two other states, such that

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle, \quad |\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = 1. \quad (2.12)$$

The wave function used in the previous section as an example, in 2.1, described a qubit. Since the squared coefficients have to add up to 1, a qubit can be represented on a radius-one sphere called Bloch's sphere (see 4) where the angles can be used to parametrize the qubit as

$$|\psi\rangle = \cos(\theta/2) |0\rangle + e^{i\phi} \sin(\theta/2) |1\rangle. \quad (2.13)$$

Quantum computers are built on systems of qubits. When concatenating various qubits, interesting properties emerge, such as entanglement. Different frameworks or quantum computing techniques exist: gate-based, measurement-based, adiabatic, and topological quantum computing. This thesis relies on *gate-based quantum*

computing, which is built on quantum circuits. A single qubit lies in a 2D Hilbert

Figure 4: Bloch's sphere. Picture taken from *Quantum Computer Music: Foundations, Methods and Advanced Concepts*. The Bloch sphere uses spherical coordinates because they naturally describe the quantum state of a qubit.

space. If multiple qubits are concatenated and a larger Hilbert space is composed through their basis vectors, a Hilbert space of dimension 2^n is built, with n being the number of qubits. Example 4 shows how two 2D qubit spaces can build a 4D one.

Quantum Circuits & Gates

A *quantum circuit* is a system composed of a series of qubits on which operations called *gates* are applied, similar to the operations applied to bits in classical computing (see Example 6). Gates in a quantum circuit correspond to matrices in linear algebra. Essentially, qubits are vectors to which linear operations are applied within a Hilbert space. The gates used for the experiments in this thesis are four:

- NOT gate (**X**): the Pauli-X gate, also known as the X gate or quantum NOT gate, is a single-qubit gate that flips the state of a qubit. Specifically, it maps $|0\rangle$ to $|1\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ to $|0\rangle$. This operation is analogous to the classical NOT gate

and does not introduce entanglement, and the matrix representation is

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.14)$$

- Hadamard gate (**H**): the Hadamard gate, denoted as H , is a fundamental single-qubit gate in quantum computing. It creates a superposition of the input qubit's state. When applied, it transforms the basis states as follows: $|0\rangle$ becomes $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle)$ and $|1\rangle$ becomes $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle - |1\rangle)$. This operation does not have a classical equivalent and can not introduce entanglement, and the matrix representation is

$$H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.15)$$

- Conditional NOT gate (**CX**): the Controlled NOT gate, often referred to as the CNOT or CX gate, is a two-qubit gate. It performs a NOT operation on the target qubit only when the control qubit is in the $|1\rangle$ state. If the control qubit is $|0\rangle$, the target qubit remains unchanged. This operation is analogous to the classical CNOT gate and can introduce entanglement, and the matrix representation is

$$CX = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.16)$$

- Toffoli gate (**CCX**): the Toffoli gate, also known as the CCNOT or CCX gate, is a three-qubit gate. It applies a NOT operation to the target qubit if and only if both control qubits are in the $|1\rangle$ state. This operation is analogous to the classical Toffoli gate and can introduce entanglement, and the matrix

representation is

$$CCX = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.17)$$

Notice that the dimension of the matrix depends on the number of qubits it is applied to. Table 1 summarizes the properties of these gates.

GATES	X Gate	H Gate	CX Gate	CCX Gate
Name	NOT	Hadamard	CNOT	CCNOT
Symbol				
Matrix	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$
Qubits applied to	1	1	2	3
Description	Flip	Superposition	Conditional flip	Double-condition flip
Classical equivalent	Yes	No	Yes	Yes

Table 1: Gates Summary Table.

Example 6

Here is a simple example formed by three qubits where different types of gates are applied. The circuit is to be read from left to right:

The three qubits are initialized in the state $|0\rangle$. In this example, the X gate is applied to the first qubit q_0 , so that it transforms into the state $|1\rangle$. A Hadamard gate (H) is applied to q_1 and q_2 , which induces a superposition state on each of these qubits. There is one additional gate: the CX gate. It is applied twice. The qubits q_2 and q_1 are the control ones respectively, and q_1 and q_0 are the targets. After all of the operations are applied, the three qubits are measured.

There exists, among others, an open-source quantum computing development software created by IBM that allows the creation of quantum circuits using different gates under a specified number of qubits. This software is called *Qiskit* [26] and it is the one used in this thesis.

Quantum Advantage & Quantum Hardware

Quantum computing is particularly interesting due to the probabilistic correlations created by superposition and entanglement during linear operations. These correlations enable quantum computers to solve specific problems that classical computers cannot, a phenomenon known as *quantum advantage*. Quantum advantage is particularly useful in fields such as cryptography, optimization, and material science. A well-known example is Shor's algorithm [27], which can factor large integers exponentially faster than any classical algorithm, solving a task that is otherwise computationally hard for classical systems. The exploration of quantum advantage

Figure 5: Picture of a real quantum computer [29].

in audio processing and music applications is still an open area of research within Quantum Computer Music.

Quantum advantage is currently limited by the hardware that researchers have been able to build. Several different types of *quantum hardware* exist (see example of a real computer in 5), each using different physical systems to implement qubits and quantum operations. The primary types of quantum hardware are superconducting qubits, trapped ions, topological qubits, photonic qubits, quantum dots, NC center qubits and NMR qubits [28]. Among these types, the hardware used in this thesis employs superconducting qubits. Typically, researchers connect remotely to quantum computers by booking time slots in a queue, as the companies owning real quantum computers are still limited.

Quantum computing is rapidly advancing, with companies like IBM, Google, Microsoft, and D-Wave developing quantum computers with tens to over a hundred qubits. However, these computers face significant limitations due to complex engineering challenges. Manipulating and concatenating various physical systems as qubits is difficult because quantum processes occur in isolated systems. Quantum systems are easily perturbed, leading to decoherence, which forces wave functions to

collapse, thus losing superposition. This makes scaling systems of qubits challenging. Additionally, errors are easily introduced during the crafting of these systems, and error mitigation remains an ongoing challenge for quantum computing researchers.

Once the principles of Quantum Computing have been introduced, it is time to delve into the theory of quantum random walks, which is the core concept on which this thesis is developed.

2.2.3 Quantum Random Walks

A *Quantum Random Walk* [30] is a random walk path that incorporates quantum principles into the process of generating the path. Quantum Random Walks can be either *continuous* or *discrete* (see 6). When the path is continuous, an evolution operator can be applied at any time to the wave function to determine its development throughout time. By contrast, when an evolution operator can be only applied in discrete time steps, the path is discrete. This is analogous to the difference between classical continuous and discrete trajectories. For this thesis, Discrete Quantum Random Walks are implemented.

Figure 6: Random Walks classification.

2.2.4 1D Discrete Quantum Random Walks

Let's define now the mathematical spaces under which a simple 1 Dimensional Discrete Quantum Random Walk operates.

A 1 Dimensional Discrete Quantum Random Walk lives on a Hilbert space that is

composed by two other Hilbert spaces: the *walker positions space*, \mathcal{H}_p , and the *coin space*, \mathcal{H}_c ,

$$\mathcal{H} = \mathcal{H}_p \otimes \mathcal{H}_c. \quad (2.18)$$

The path is one dimensional because the walker space only allows to take steps forward or backwards in one dimension (in the x axis), and this is not to be confused with the dimensions of the Hilbert spaces involved. The walker space is defined by a set of position basis states $|i\rangle_p$ that generate all of the possible position states available in the space

$$|\psi\rangle_p = \sum_i \alpha_i |i\rangle_p, \quad \sum_i |\alpha_i|^2 = 1. \quad (2.19)$$

On the other hand, the coin space has only two basis states ($|0\rangle \equiv |\text{heads}\rangle$ or $|1\rangle \equiv |\text{tails}\rangle$). The coin wave functions are defined as follows

$$|\psi\rangle_c = \alpha_1 |\text{heads}\rangle + \alpha_2 |\text{tails}\rangle, \quad \alpha_1^2 + \alpha_2^2 = 1. \quad (2.20)$$

Thus, the global wave function obtained after composing the two Hilbert spaces is

$$|\psi\rangle = |\psi\rangle_p \otimes |\psi\rangle_c. \quad (2.21)$$

In a classical random walk, a coin is tossed at each position to determine whether to move forward or backward. In a quantum random walk, however, all possible paths are simultaneously preserved in superposition until a measurement is made, with progress occurring in all possible directions. A quantum walk exhibits *memory*, as it considers all possibilities at once.

To move through the Hilbert space, operators are applied to a given state vector, equivalent to a wave function. To implement a quantum random walk, an operator that encodes the act of tossing the coin is first required, followed by a second operator that encodes taking a step either forward or backward. The coin toss operator, C , is defined as follows

$$C = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\text{heads}\rangle\langle\text{heads}| + |\text{heads}\rangle\langle\text{tails}| + |\text{tails}\rangle\langle\text{heads}| - |\text{tails}\rangle\langle\text{tails}|). \quad (2.22)$$

The operator C has been chosen to be the Hadamard operator H in this thesis, which induces a superposition of two states on a given state vector if it is not already in a superposition. In this case, it induces a superposition of the coin states $|\text{heads}\rangle$ and $|\text{tails}\rangle$.

The shift operator S , on the other hand, encodes the act of taking steps

$$S = \sum_x (|x+1\rangle\langle x| \otimes |\text{heads}\rangle\langle\text{heads}| + |x-1\rangle\langle x| \otimes |\text{tails}\rangle\langle\text{tails}|). \quad (2.23)$$

Since movement forward or backward depends on the coin's outcome, this operator is constructed through the composition between the position basis vectors and the coin's, and it can introduce entanglement and create non-separable states.

Movement through space is a composition of these two operators, S and H , and the total evolution operator is defined as

$$U = S \cdot (C \otimes I). \quad (2.24)$$

By inspection of the operator U , it is observed that the coin-tossing operation is applied first, then scaled up through an identity matrix to match the size of the space, and finally, the step operator is applied. This means that first the coin is tossed, and then the output dictates the step taking forward. See Example 7 for an illustration of these operators being applied to a state to generate progress in a 1D Quantum Random Walk.

Example 7

Let $|\psi\rangle$ be the initial state from which a step is taken forward within a 1D

Discrete Quantum Random Walk

$$|\psi\rangle = |\text{heads}\rangle \otimes |x\rangle,$$

where $|\text{heads}\rangle$ is the initial contribution to the wave function from the coin space and $|x\rangle$ is the contribution from the position space. Applying the coin operator, the result is

$$(C \otimes I) |\psi\rangle = \frac{(|\text{heads}\rangle + |\text{tails}\rangle) \otimes |x\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}.$$

After the coin operator, the shift operator is applied

$$S(C \otimes I) |\psi\rangle = \frac{(|\text{heads}\rangle \otimes |x+1\rangle) + |\text{tails}\rangle \otimes |x-1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}.$$

A superposition of the two possible directions in which the step can be taken appears after applying the operators. If more steps are taken, the operators should be applied again consecutively until the walk is finished. When the walk finishes, the wave function is measured, and thus collapsed.

2.2.5 2D Discrete Quantum Random Walks

A 2D Discrete Quantum Random Walk works similarly to the one-dimensional version, but now the walker can move along two axes. For this reason, the coin does not have just two outcomes, but four instead: $|\text{top-right}\rangle \equiv |\nearrow\rangle$, $|\text{top-left}\rangle \equiv |\nwarrow\rangle$, $|\text{down-right}\rangle \equiv |\searrow\rangle$, and $|\text{down-left}\rangle \equiv |\swarrow\rangle$. Consequently, the C operator is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} C \otimes C = & \frac{1}{\sqrt{4}} (|\nearrow\rangle \langle \nearrow| + |\nearrow\rangle \langle \nwarrow| + |\nearrow\rangle \langle \searrow| + |\nearrow\rangle \langle \swarrow| \\ & + |\nwarrow\rangle \langle \nearrow| - |\nwarrow\rangle \langle \nwarrow| + |\nwarrow\rangle \langle \searrow| - |\nwarrow\rangle \langle \swarrow| \\ & + |\searrow\rangle \langle \nearrow| + |\searrow\rangle \langle \nwarrow| - |\searrow\rangle \langle \searrow| - |\searrow\rangle \langle \swarrow| \\ & + |\swarrow\rangle \langle \nearrow| - |\swarrow\rangle \langle \nwarrow| - |\swarrow\rangle \langle \searrow| + |\swarrow\rangle \langle \swarrow|), \end{aligned} \quad (2.25)$$

where $|00\rangle \equiv |\nearrow\rangle$, $|01\rangle \equiv |\nwarrow\rangle$, $|10\rangle \equiv |\searrow\rangle$ and $|11\rangle \equiv |\swarrow\rangle$. Operator S also addresses the new axis by including y coordinates,

$$S = \sum_{x,y} (|x+1, y+1\rangle\langle x, y| \otimes |\nearrow\rangle\langle \nearrow| + |x-1, y+1\rangle\langle x, y| \otimes |\nwarrow\rangle\langle \nwarrow|) \\ + \sum_{x,y} (|x+1, y-1\rangle\langle x, y| \otimes |\searrow\rangle\langle \searrow| + |x-1, y-1\rangle\langle x, y| \otimes |\swarrow\rangle\langle \swarrow|). \quad (2.26)$$

The evolution operator is again the product of these two operators

$$U = S \cdot (C \otimes I). \quad (2.27)$$

The arrow kets and bras can also be relabeled to clarify which qubit states are handling the heads and tails options for each axis, as follows

$$\mathcal{H}_c = \text{span}\{|h\rangle, |t\rangle\} \\ |h_{cx}h_{cy}\rangle = |\nearrow\rangle, |h_{cx}t_{cy}\rangle = |\nwarrow\rangle, \\ |h_{cy}t_{cx}\rangle = |\swarrow\rangle, |t_{cx}t_{cy}\rangle = |\searrow\rangle. \quad (2.28)$$

For the purposes of this thesis, some rearrangement of the qubits in these 2D quantum random walk operators must be performed. Later on, in section 3.1.1, it is explained in more detail why this rearrangement is important. In a nutshell, the operators and qubits must be arranged in a way that allows the decomposition of the 2D quantum walk into two 1D quantum random walks, such that

$$U_{1\otimes 1} = S_{1\otimes 1} \cdot (I_x \otimes C_x \otimes I_y \otimes C_y). \quad (2.29)$$

However, equation 2.27, expressed as tensor products, looks instead like this

$$U = S \cdot (C \otimes I) = S \cdot (C_x \otimes C_y \otimes I_x \otimes I_y). \quad (2.30)$$

This decomposition in 2.30 does not match the one in 2.29 and thus does not account for the $1D \otimes 1D$ decomposition. For the unitary operator to be decomposed in such

a way, the shift operator must adhere to the following expression

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{1\otimes 1} &= (S_{-x} \otimes H_x + S_{+x} \otimes T_x) \otimes (S_{-y} \otimes H_y + S_{+y} \otimes T_y) \\
&= (S_{-x} \otimes H_x) \otimes (S_{-y} \otimes H_y) + (S_{-x} \otimes H_x) \otimes (S_{+y} \otimes T_y) \\
&\quad + (S_{+x} \otimes T_x) \otimes (S_{-y} \otimes H_y) + (S_{+x} \otimes T_x) \otimes (S_{+y} \otimes T_y). \tag{2.31}
\end{aligned}$$

In this expression, S_{-x} indicates the position projector that shifts the x-axis one step to the left, while H_x is the coin projector that encodes the $|\text{heads}\rangle$ output of the coin within the x-axis. S_{+x} indicates the act of taking a step to the right, and T_x encodes the tails $|\text{tails}\rangle$ output. Analogous reasoning follows for the rest of the projectors in this expression. This shift operator is different from the one in 2.26. For clarity, following the same notation as in 2.28, these coin projectors expand in the following manner

$$H_x = |h_{cx}\rangle \langle h_{cx}|, H_y = |h_{cy}\rangle \langle h_{cy}|, T_x = |t_{cx}\rangle \langle t_{cx}|, T_y = |t_{cy}\rangle \langle t_{cy}|, \tag{2.32}$$

and the position ones expand as

$$S_{+x} = |x+1\rangle \langle x|, S_{-x} = |x-1\rangle \langle x|, S_{+y} = |y+1\rangle \langle y|, S_{-y} = |y-1\rangle \langle y|. \tag{2.33}$$

If there is a one-to-one mapping of the basis states of two spaces, it means that there also exists a mapping between the qubit arrangements of any two operators given in these two spaces. Thus, the following mapping or swap between the qubits

$$swap : |q_{cx}, q_{cy}, q_{x1}, q_{x2}, q_{x3}, q_{y1}, q_{y2}, q_{y3}\rangle \mapsto |q_{x1}, q_{x2}, q_{x3}, q_{cx}, q_{y1}, q_{y2}, q_{y3}, q_{cy}\rangle, \tag{2.34}$$

demonstrates that the shift operator can be written as shown in 2.31, and so is the evolution operator in 2.29.

2.2.6 QRWs in Music: State of the Art

As mentioned in 1.1, there are only a few references that have used quantum computing algorithms for music applications. In particular, only two chapters within

the book [2] exploit the concept of quantum random walk.

In chapter 3, the notion of quantum random walk is derived from the classical intuitions of classical random walks and Markov Chains. Then, a system of 3 qubits is mapped to a cube to design a simple quantum walk through its vertices. Later on, in chapter 4, discrete quantum random walks are explained in more detail and used to generate simple melodies.

This thesis aims to extend this work. Firstly, a more robust mathematical formalism for larger systems of qubits in the shape of a quantum random walk intended to encode musical information is introduced. This sets a proof of concept and leads to a scalable protocol on how to use a large number of positions and coins by using several qubits to deal with musical spaces.

Furthermore, a solid mapping on how to encode 2D planes of data designed for musical applications as quantum states is explained. Similar to the encoding of the vertices of a cube in chapter 3, this is an extended work for a more complex geometry: an x-y discrete grid, composed of a significantly larger number of positions.

Since music technology nowadays deals with large databases with multidimensional features, designing algorithms to explore these multidimensional spaces becomes a very promising proposal.

Chapter 3

Methodology & Results

The methodologies to implement and sonify the quantum random walks within rhythmspheres are divided into three stages, as shown in Figure 7: Stage 1 describes the design of quantum random walk algorithms as quantum circuits, how they are remotely executed on quantum computers, and how they are mapped to the rhythmphere. Stage 2 details the introduction of potential fields into the rhythmphere to influence paths and create shapes and trajectories. In this stage, the concept of *Quantum Feedback* is introduced, which links the potential biases with the circuits designed in the previous stage. Stage 3 outlines the sonification mappings and how the paths are transformed into MIDI messages to be sent to Cubase, a Digital Audio Workstation. The Python code for the three stages can be found in this *GitHub repository*, inside the example folder.

3.1 Stage 1: From Hilbert spaces to Rhythmspheres

This first stage outlines the process of creating quantum walks as quantum circuits and designing the mappings that connect the qubits' Hilbert space with the rhythmphere. The circuits are implemented in Python using Qiskit. Once created, they are executed by remotely connecting to real quantum computing hardware. The results are then retrieved and stored in lists to be used for path generation.

Figure 7: Diagram of the 3 stages for the implementation and sonification of quantum random walks in rhythmspaces.

3.1.1 Encoding positions in the rhythmspace as qubits

This thesis aims to map quantum random walks to a rhythmspace, and for this purpose, before building the circuits, an efficient mapping between the qubit space and the rhythmspace must be designed, such that quantum random walks can be represented in this percussive grid.

Finding an appropriate mapping is not trivial. The number of qubits to be used is limited by the available computational power of the quantum machines provided for this project. A reasonable range of qubits to use, which is not constrained by these resources, is 6 to 10 qubits. In this case, 8 qubits are used: 6 of them encode the walker positions in the quantum random walk Hilbert space, and the remaining 2 encode the coin.

To achieve an efficient mapping between the qubits and the rhythmspace, the qubits should be arranged such that the space they generate is organized as a 2D grid. One possible arrangement is

$$\begin{aligned}
 |x, y\rangle_p &= |q_1 q_2 q_3, q_4 q_5 q_6\rangle, \\
 x &= 2^2 q_1 + 2^1 q_2 + 2^0 q_3, \\
 y &= 2^2 q_4 + 2^1 q_5 + 2^0 q_6.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.1}$$

where the position qubits are separated into two groups of 3, each encoding one axis of the rhythmspace. This arrangement for the position qubits keeps the two axes separated, allowing the positions to be expressed as a composition of two one-dimensional quantum random walks

$$\mathcal{H}_p = \mathcal{H}_{px} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{py}. \quad (3.2)$$

Separating the two axes is crucial for implementing the quantum walks as quantum circuits, as it significantly reduces the number of gates needed. Since the position qubits are separated into two axes, the coin space must also conform to this decomposition, differentiating the one-dimensional quantum random walks

$$\begin{aligned} |x, y\rangle_c &= |q_7, q_8\rangle, \\ \mathcal{H}_c &= \mathcal{H}_{cx} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{cy}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

and thus the total space can be expressed as

$$\mathcal{H} = (\mathcal{H}_{px} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{py}) \otimes (\mathcal{H}_{cx} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{cy}). \quad (3.4)$$

Applying the swap in 2.34,

$$\mathcal{H}_{2D} = \mathcal{H}_{1D,x} \otimes \mathcal{H}_{1D,y}. \quad (3.5)$$

3.1.2 Handling the pixel resolution

Once the encoding of positions in the rhythmspace as elements in Hilbert space is established, certain resolution-related aspects must be addressed.

Taking steps in a 2D quantum random walk means that at every step, the space grid of size N grows as

$$N = (2T + 1) \cdot (2T + 1), \quad (3.6)$$

where T is the number of steps. Taking 3 steps creates a grid of 49 positions (see

Figure 8). Taking 4 steps would already surpass the available positions in the qubit space, since the walker space is formed by 6 qubits, and it has $2^6 = 64$ positions. Thus, the quantum random walks are constrained to 3 steps, such that the qubits space has enough positions to encode it. After these 3 steps, the wave function is measured, collapsed and sonified, which means that a rhythm is heard every 3 steps.

On the other hand, the rhythm space is a 2D grid formed by 500 pixels. A correspondence between the pixels in the rhythm space and the quantum space must be defined. The 49 positions do not cover the entire grid of pixels of the rhythm space. A solution to implement the quantum walks in this space consists of shifting and updating the window or grid of size N as the path progresses through the rhythm space, such that it is always centered at the given position in this classical space (see Figure 9). In addition, the pixels do not necessarily need to be mapped one-to-one to the positions in the walker Hilbert space. For example, there can be 3 pixels for every qubit square, which means that in the $7 \times 7 = 49$ grid, there are $(3 \times 6) \cdot (3 \times 6)$ pixels.

Figure 8: Illustration of the 49 positions of the quantum walk within the qubit space. An example of a 3-step walk is shown. The variable n represents the pixels within a square of this qubit grid, and in this work, n is set to 10.

In this thesis, a shifting window with a pixel space to Hilbert space ratio of $n = 10$ was selected. This ratio was determined by computing the distances between all

pairs of points in the rhythmspace used for interpolation. A significant number of these distances fall within the range of 0 to 0.2 (0-100 on the 500-pixel scale), indicating that a ratio between 0 and 100 pixels is reasonable (see Figure 10).

Figure 9: Qubits' window updating as the path in the rhythmspace progresses.

Figure 10: Histogram of the distances within the rhythmspace.

3.1.3 Implementing the circuits

Now that the encodings and the resolutions have been described, it is time to dive into the crafting of the circuits. To implement the quantum circuits that encode the quantum random walk paths, a deeper understanding of the matrix representation of these paths is convenient, since gates in a quantum circuit are equivalent to matrices.

Firstly, let's study the matrix representation for the 1-dimensional case. The coin operator, as explained in section 2.2.4, is a Hadamard operator equivalent to an H gate

$$H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.7)$$

The shift operator maps a vector x to either $x + 1$ or $x - 1$. This shifting can be expressed in a matrix as (right shifting case)

$$U_{\text{right}} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.8)$$

For the 2D quantum random walk case, a similar structure can be followed: the coin operator can be a 4×4 Hadamard operator and a shift operator that encodes the operations $y \rightarrow y + 1$ and $y \rightarrow y - 1$ as well.

However, when building the matrices for the 2D case, it is important to achieve a representation that minimizes the number of gates needed. Decomposing a large operator into a set of simple quantum gates is very demanding in terms of quantum computational resources. If the process previously followed for the 1D case is followed again without taking this aspect into consideration, the resulting matrix can require thousands of gates, whereas a practical number is typically under 100.

Another challenge is finding a good decomposition algorithm to express the matrix into gates. The process followed in this thesis to address this issue had different phases, explained here to guide future authors on optimizing the number of gates:

1. **First approach:** The matrix form shown in the previous equation was inserted into the `transpile()` function in Qiskit to decompose it into a set of universal gates. The resulting number of gates was in the thousands. This matrix representation and the decomposition algorithm in this function did not work.
2. **Second approach:** Open-source algorithms, such as the one referenced in [31], were tested. This algorithm reduced the number of gates from thousands to hundreds compared to the previous approach.
3. **Third approach:** If the 2D quantum walk is decomposed into two 1D quantum walks, a simple circuit implementation with a small number of gates, as demonstrated in [32], can be used. The matrix representations and decomposition methods are explained in detail there, and the proof that a 2D walk can be composed of two 1D walks is provided in Section 2.2.5. Therefore, the circuit used in this thesis, based on the decomposition in [32], is as follows:

By inspecting the circuit, it can be observed that the structure is repeated twice. Qubits 0-3 handle the first 1D quantum walk, while qubits 4-7 handle the second one. Qubits 3 and 7 correspond to the coins, as the coins are

encoded through Hadamard gates in this thesis. Qubits 0-2 encode the x axis, and 4-6 the y one.

Since three steps will be implemented for each quantum circuit run, this circuit must be concatenated three times before measurement. Once the circuits are remotely executed and measured on real quantum hardware, the results can be stored in a list for post-processing to construct the quantum paths in the classical rhythm space.

3.2 Stage 2: Biasing with potentials

After the previous mappings are defined, the second stage generates the paths and plots them. Animations of the sequence being generated are also outputted.

In physics, paths are rarely free and are usually influenced by forces and potential fields. Potential fields dependent on the position (x,y) of the rhythm space are used here to bias the evolution of the quantum random walks.

The crucial aspect of these potentials is that they are tasked with altering the probabilities of the quantum superposition state. Typically, classical continuous paths are simply modified by the gradient of the potential, which indicates the direction of the evolution through the derivative. However, how can a potential dictate the direction of a superposition of possibilities in quantum states?

The solution is to alter the probability distribution of the wave functions by modifying the prepared states and the circuits. If the probability distribution, which designates probabilities for the different superposed directions, is dependent on the gradient of the potential, then the potential is biasing the quantum random walks. In other words, a "quantum feedback" is induced, in which the evolution of the path under a potential field directly tunes the probability distributions of the wave functions in a Hilbert space (see Figure 10). Let's study this feedback in more detail across the following subsections.

Figure 11: A simple diagram illustrating how the quantum feedback induced by a potential field tunes the probability distribution of the states of a given wave function. In this example, the tuning favors states 3 and 4, indicating that the potential is enhancing their corresponding positions in the rhythmspace.

3.2.1 Quantum feedback based on potential gradients

In this thesis, the term quantum feedback refers to the connection between the gradient of the position at one step in the rhythmspace and the quantum circuits applied to it to generate the next step of the path.

Figure 12: Quantum Feedback algorithm steps.

In Figure 12, the steps followed by the algorithm to generate a new position are illustrated. The iterative algorithm takes the value of the potential field V at a point (x, y) within the rhythm space grid. It then computes the gradient vector

of this potential by applying the finite differences method with respect to the two variables. The gradient tuple values are normalized to the range 0-1.

Once normalized, the gradient tuple is used to interpolate the values of the angles required to prepare the new state vector to be input into the quantum circuit. This interpolation follows the expression

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Phi_{i,x} &= (1 - t_x)\Phi_{min} + t_x\Phi_{max} \\
 \Theta_{i,x} &= (1 - t_x)\Theta_{min} + t_x\Theta_{max} \\
 \Phi_{i,y} &= (1 - t_y)\Phi_{min} + t_y\Phi_{max} \\
 \Theta_{i,y} &= (1 - t_y)\Theta_{min} + t_y\Theta_{max},
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.9}$$

where (t_x, t_y) is the normalized gradient tuple. These angles are used to apply rotations to the coin qubit in each 1D quantum random walk within the main circuit. There are two angles, Φ and Θ , per axis. These rotations alter the initial state vector in such a way that the probability distribution of the possible outputs, after measuring the wave function, is modified. Essentially, the potential field tunes the possible outputs of the circuit at each step. Although the same four possible outputs can be measured, the probability of each one changes at every step. The potential field directly biases the probabilities, creating a feedback loop between the gradient and the probability distributions in the circuit.

To interpolate the angle values in Equation 3.9, a classical optimization through gradient descent is performed on the circuit, defining a cost function to establish the boundaries of the angles $\Phi_{min}, \Phi_{max}, \Theta_{min}$ and Θ_{max} .

In the following subsections, different potential field scenarios are explored that include the quantum feedback algorithm.

3.2.2 Purely Random Paths

In this case, the potential is zero, and there is no position-dependent gradient to bias the probability distribution of the quantum walks in a given direction, as it is

shown in Figure 13. This is the simplest scenario where all directions are equally probable.

$$V(x, y) = 0. \quad (3.10)$$

Figure 13: This figure illustrates a quantum random walk path. Since the potential is zero, no bias is induced in any specific direction, and the walk just wanders around without a specific pattern.

3.2.3 Linear Potential

A linear potential induces paths that follow a line towards the minimum energy regions in the space. In this case, the quantum feedback biases the probability distribution towards a given direction. Notice that a classical path would strictly follow a line. However, a quantum path introduces a certain probability at every given step of following different directions. The key idea here is that the probability of the direction imposed by the potential is higher. This yields trajectories that, despite following a potential, introduce some chaos and randomness, making the sonification special and interesting.

The linear potential is expressed as

$$V(y) = ky, \quad (3.11)$$

and in this thesis the k value has been chosen to be $k = 1$. Figure 14 illustrates an example of a path under this potential.

Figure 14: The path is biased along the y -axis. Since it is a quantum random walk, small deviations at every step can be observed as a result of the probability distributions of wave functions. However, the potential bias still dominates, inducing directionality.

3.2.4 Gaussian Potential

The Gaussian potential sets a potential well. If the path approaches the well, it will progressively fall into it. The fall will not be direct, since there is a certain probability of avoiding it at each step, but the bias will always favor advancement towards the deepest region of the well.

The Gaussian potential in a 2D xy plane can be expressed as

$$V(x, y) = V_0 \exp\left(-\frac{(x - x_0)^2}{2\sigma_x^2} - \frac{(y - y_0)^2}{2\sigma_y^2}\right). \quad (3.12)$$

where, V_0 is the amplitude of the potential, x_0, y_0 are the coordinates of the center of the Gaussian potential, and σ_x, σ_y are the standard deviations in the x and y directions, respectively. In this thesis, V_0 has been chosen to be 100, $x_0 = y_0 = 0$, and $\sigma_x = \sigma_y = 100$. An example of a path generated under this potential is shown

in Figure 15.

Figure 15: The Gaussian potential creates a well into which the path falls when approached. Despite being a quantum walk, the probability distribution is unable to escape the well due to the higher weight privileging the gradient descent.

3.2.5 Gaussian Potential: Inertial Dynamics

So far, quantum feedback does not account for accelerations. If inertia is included within the equations, second-order paths are induced. This is what happens, for example, when planets orbit potential wells created by stars in space due to gravitational accelerations.

In more detail, the equations used for the non-inertial case update the positions as follows

$$\begin{aligned}x' &= x + \Delta x \\y' &= y + \Delta y,\end{aligned}$$

where the accelerations are zero and the positions simply evolve through a delta. In

contrast, the inertial case updates positions in the following way

$$v'_x = v_x + a_x \Delta t, \quad v'_y = v_y + a_y \Delta t$$

$$x' = x + v'_x \cdot \Delta t, \quad y' = y + v'_y \cdot \Delta t.$$

Here, the potential bias controls the accelerations instead of doing it directly on the positions.

Notice that quantum paths do not draw perfect closed orbits around the Gaussian well; instead, they have a certain probability of altering the orbit at each step. If the bias is subtle enough, the quantum path will be able to draw a pseudo-closed orbit, which resembles a classical one but introduces variations.

Figure 16: As the path approaches the well, it gains inertia and starts drawing a curve around it. In classical conditions, the path would describe a perfectly symmetrical orbit. Nevertheless, the quantum walk perturbs the orbit, introducing quantum randomness that deforms it.

3.3 Stage 3: Sonification

The final stage of the methodology involves sonifying the quantum walks by encoding them as MIDI messages and sending them to a Digital Audio Workstation. The

audio files of the paths can then be exported from the DAW and added to the animation videos of the trajectories.

3.3.1 Resampling the paths for sonification

Each point in the rhythm space is associated with a rhythmic pattern. The paths are formed by a series of dots generated through quantum walks. However, sonification is not directly achieved by using the rhythms at these points. Instead, the path is resampled to align with a chosen semiquaver grid, ensuring that the rhythmic evolution is coherent and smooth.

Once the resampled path is computed, the rhythmic patterns corresponding to each point are generated. To build the final rhythmic sequence, a single beat from each pattern at each resampled dot must be selected.

Figure 17: The black line represents the initial quantum path. The blue dots indicate the resampled path that aligns with the imposed semiquaver grid for the rhythm. Each resampled dot contains a MIDI pattern. The beat corresponding to the specific moment in the grid is extracted from the pattern and used to construct the final rhythm. This figure illustrates an 8-semiquaver grid for simplicity, but the grid used in this thesis is instead a 16-semiquaver one.

The beat chosen within each pattern is the one that aligns with the global beat of

the grid. A beat within a pattern consists of a list of percussive instruments to be triggered at that moment. Therefore, all the selected beats contain the information about which instruments should be triggered at each instant or semiquaver of the percussive grid. Figure 17 illustrates this resampling process.

The lists of instruments to be triggered, corresponding to the selected beats, are encoded in the MIDI protocol and sent to a DAW to produce sound. The next section explains how these MIDI strings are handled in the DAW, which in this case is Cubase.

3.3.2 Sending the paths as MIDI messages

The MIDI messages received in the DAW create percussive patterns that trigger different instruments at each beat. Therefore, the sequence of patterns must align with the DAW's beat grid, with the MIDI strings being sent at time intervals that correspond to this grid.

Figure 18: Cubase interface with an imported MIDI file from the rhythmspace.

Once the MIDI strings arrive at the DAW, they are sonified using plugins that follow the General MIDI Percussion Map labeling (see table on page 6 in [33]). By convention, different MIDI notes correspond to different percussive instruments. Thus, each MIDI string triggers a specific set of instruments at a given time. Figure 18

provides an example of an imported MIDI string of a path, illustrating the interface of Cubase.

Examples of various sonified quantum random walks in a rhythmspace under different potential field conditions can be visualized and heard here: *Click here to watch the videos*. These animations were generated by exporting the audio from Cubase and attaching them to the videos created with Python.

Chapter 4

Discussion & Conclusion

This thesis details the process of developing more complex quantum random walk algorithms for sonification purposes, resulting in a proof-of-concept tool that facilitates the exploration and understanding of quantum walks through sound. Each objective in 1.2 is discussed in more detail below.

Objective 1 Discussion: Quantum Random Walk Algorithms for Music Generation

The first objective, which sought the development of scalable and robust algorithms that leverage quantum random walks to generate music, it has been fulfilled. This work describes a method that carefully exploits the symmetries in the problem to build robust and efficient algorithms that minimize the number of qubits and gates used, accounting for the current limitations in the existing hardware. These algorithms are also scalable, allowing the procedures to be easily expanded to larger systems of qubits. For example, the mappings between the Hilbert space and the rhythms space can easily accommodate higher-dimensional Hilbert spaces, and the windows and resolutions can be adjusted to specific problems.

While there is extensive literature on quantum random walks and quantum computing, references specifically focused on designing these types of algorithms for music creation remain limited, as mentioned in 2.2.6. The algorithms in this thesis suc-

cessfully expand the techniques in those references to a more complex geometry, in this case, a 2D plane.

Designing algorithms with a creative purpose requires a different mindset and calls for unique algorithmic techniques to address specific challenges. From the outset, this thesis applies quantum random walk algorithms to interactive interfaces and sound, inherently aligning the development process with artistic perspectives. This artistic viewpoint is one of the core focuses within the field of Quantum Computer Music.

Since quantum computing is still limited by the current existing and available hardware, for future work, it would be interesting to expand these algorithms when more powerful computers become available and to rethink them in this new scenario.

Objectives 2 & 3 Discussion: Sonification for Physics Research & for Public Understanding of Physics

Researchers can benefit from approaches like the one explained in this document to gain insight into abstract quantum computing algorithms, specifically the formalism of quantum random walks. Encoding information using qubits for artistic purposes opens new avenues for exploring physics and boosts interdisciplinary connections between art and science. Visualizing abstract concepts through art can help trigger the correct intuitions in researchers if the sonification mappings are designed intelligently, ensuring that these abstract concepts are accurately conveyed through sound.

To study in more detail whether the algorithms developed here do trigger the right intuitions, user-based tests could be conducted to evaluate the kinds of cognitive interpretations that can be achieved. This would involve tuning the potential fields and algorithms in various ways so that quantum perturbations can be both heard and appreciated when visualized and sonified. User-based studies could provide valuable insights into how the general public, not just the research community, can interpret and benefit from complex physics concepts through music.

Objective 4 Discussion: New Methods for Creating Sounds and Composing Music

As mentioned and demonstrated throughout this work, the field of quantum computing possesses properties that are inherently different in nature from those of classical computers. The quantum random walks used here exploit superposition and entanglement, generating music in a completely novel way. Sound generated with quantum computers is fundamentally different because it relies on different mathematical formalisms.

When more powerful computers become available, the algorithms developed here could be extended to further explore these unique properties. For example, measurements could be performed after more steps, potentially even hundreds, instead of just three, to amplify the quantum effects. Additionally, more qubits and gates could be utilized to enhance these quantum properties.

Objective 5 Discussion: Interactive Interfaces for Exploring Physics Concepts

The final objective focused on developing user-interactive interfaces for exploring physics concepts. Currently, interaction requires accessing the code and manually changing the parameters for the quantum paths and potentials. Ideally, this project would evolve to allow users to explore these parameters through accessible buttons and sliders on an interface. On the other hand, the visualization of the effects of these parameters on the paths is already being plotted and displayed through animations. The main area needing improvement is the method for modifying parameters in the code, which would benefit from a more immediate and interactive approach, but the resolution and plotting aspects have already been addressed.

It's worth reiterating the significance of the concept of quantum feedback, used to bias the paths through potential fields. This concept directly connects the visual interface and audio with the algorithms in a creative way and could be exploited in real time. The idea of manipulating an interface that somehow affects the wave

functions of the qubits is a promising approach for exploring quantum algorithms through art.

Other Conclusions & General Thoughts

A rhythm space is a multidimensional musical space. Various other music datasets could be arranged and interpolated to create different types of spaces. The quantum algorithms in this thesis can operate on any musical space; they are not strictly bound to a rhythm space. The key requirement is that the space is robust and creatively interesting, making it worthwhile to explore quantum paths within it.

Lastly, a rhythm space can also be viewed as a method for encoding and decoding audio, similar to the function of a variational autoencoder [34]. In this context, the rhythm space serves as the "latent space". This analogy suggests the potential for connecting quantum random walks in music with Machine Learning algorithms.

Bibliography

- [1] Dargan, J. 5 crucial quantum computing applications examples. <https://thequantuminsider.com/2023/05/24/quantum-computing-applications/> (2023). Accessed: 2024-06-20.
- [2] Miranda, E. (ed.) *Quantum Computer Music: Foundations, Methods and Advanced Concepts* (Springer Nature, 2022).
- [3] 1st International Symposium on Quantum Computing and Musical Creativity (2021). URL <https://isqcmc.github.io/2021>. Accessed: 2024-03-31.
- [4] 2nd international symposium on quantum computing and musical creativity (2023). URL <https://isqcmc.github.io/Proceedings>. Accessed: 2024-03-31.
- [5] Ball, P. Can we use quantum computers to make music? <https://physicsworld.com/a/can-we-use-quantum-computers-to-make-music/> (2023). Accessed: 2024-06-20.
- [6] Miranda, E. R., Thomas, P. & Itaboraí, P. V. Q1synth: A quantum computer musical instrument. *Applied Sciences* **13**, 2386 (2023).
- [7] NAMM. Max mathews | namm.org. <https://www.namm.org/library/oral-history/max-mathews> (2024). Accessed: 2024-06-20.
- [8] Manning, P. *Electronic and Computer Music* (Oxford University Press, USA, 2013).

- [9] Diego, U. S. Miller puckette. https://music-cms.ucsd.edu/people/faculty/emeritus_faculty/miller-puckette/index.html (2024). Accessed: 2024-06-20.
- [10] BNE. Pierre schaeffer. <https://datos.bne.es/persona/XX989982.html> (2024). Accessed: 2024-06-20.
- [11] Iannis xenakis official website. URL <https://www.iannis-xenakis.org/en/>. Accessed: 2024-06-16.
- [12] BNE. Karlheinz stockhausen. <https://datos.bne.es/persona/XX4579437.html> (2024). Accessed: 2024-06-20.
- [13] Pithoprakta by iannis xenakis. URL <https://music77031su.wordpress.com/2017/04/02/pithoprakta-by-iannis-xenakis/>. Accessed: 2024-06-16.
- [14] Cohen, L. Joint probability distributions in quantum mechanics. In *Contemporary Research in the Foundations and Philosophy of Quantum Theory: Proceedings of a Conference Held at the University of Western Ontario, London, Canada*, 66–79 (Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, 1973).
- [15] Rau, J. On quantum vs. classical probability. *Annals of Physics* **324**, 2622–2637 (2009).
- [16] Yamada, R. *et al.* Applications of quantum randomness: From rabi oscillations to fourier axis controlling the musical timbre. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2109.03511* (2021). URL <https://doi.org/10.48293/IJMSTA-77>.
- [17] Gómez Marín, D. *Similarity and Style in Electronic Dance Music Drum Rhythms*. Ph.d. thesis, Universitat Pompeu Fabra (2018).
- [18] Marín, D. G. Rhythmspace demo. YouTube (2018). URL <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Wwg2XqK4vKQ>. Accessed: 2024-06-20.
- [19] Gomez-Marin, D., Jorda, S. & Herrera, P. Drum rhythm spaces: From polyphonic similarity to generative maps. *Journal of New Music Research* **49** (2020).

- [20] Turquois, C., Hermant, M., Gómez-Marín, D. & Jordà, S. Exploring the benefits of 2d visualizations for drum samples retrieval. In *Proceedings of the 2016 ACM on Conference on Human Information Interaction and Retrieval* (2016).
- [21] London, J. *Hearing in Time: Psychological Aspects of Musical Meter* (Oxford University Press, 2012).
- [22] Choubey, A. *Evaluation of Drum Rhythmspace in a Music Production Environment*. Master's thesis, Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona, Spain (2023). Master's Thesis in Sound and Music Computing.
- [23] Clark, P. *Tap to Drums: Extending Monophonically Tapped Rhythms to Polyphonic Drum Pattern Generation*. Master's thesis, Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona, Spain (2023). Master's Thesis in Sound and Music Computing.
- [24] Griffiths, D. J. & Schroeter, D. F. *Introduction to Quantum Mechanics* (Cambridge University Press, 2018).
- [25] Proving that quantum entanglement is real. <https://www.caltech.edu/about/news/proving-that-quantum-entanglement-is-real> (2022). Accessed: 2024-06-20.
- [26] Qiskit. An open-source quantum computing software framework. URL <https://qiskit.org/>. Accessed: 2024.
- [27] Classiq. Shor's algorithm explained. <https://www.classiq.io/insights/shors-algorithm-explained> (2022). Accessed: 2024-06-20.
- [28] Microsoft. Types of qubits. <https://quantum.microsoft.com/en-us/explore/concepts/types-of-qubits> (2024). Accessed: 2024-06-20.
- [29] Iqm quantum computers to deliver quantum processing units for the first spanish quantum computer. <https://www.businesswire.com/news/home/20230306005345/en/IQM> (2023). Accessed: 2024-06-20.
- [30] Venegas-Andraca, S. E. Quantum walks: A comprehensive review. *Quantum Information Processing* **11** (2012).

-
- [31] Fedimser. Quantum decomposition example. https://github.com/fedimser/quantum_decomp/blob/master/example.ipynb (2023). Accessed: 2024-06-20.
- [32] Wing-Bocanegra, A. & Venegas-Andraca, S. E. Circuit implementation of discrete-time quantum walks via the shunt decomposition method. *Quantum Information Processing* **22** (2023).
- [33] MIDI Manufacturers Association. General midi system level 1 specification. <https://midi.org/general-midi-level-1> (1994). Accessed: 2024-06-20, page 6.
- [34] IBM. Variational autoencoder. <https://www.ibm.com/think/topics/variational-autoencoder> (2024). Accessed: 2024-06-20.